

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION
AND MOTIVATION IN LEARNING ACTIVITIES: A THEORETICAL
APPROACH

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Abstract: This theoretical study examines the intricate relationship between academic procrastination and motivation in learning activities. Academic procrastination is becoming an increasingly prevalent issue in modern educational environments, impacting students' academic performance and psychological well-being. Drawing upon theoretical frameworks such as Self-Determination Theory, the study explores various types of motivation, including intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, and their influence on academic procrastination.

Keywords: Academic procrastination, procrastination, academic motivation, extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation, amotivation.

Introduction. In modern society, academic procrastination is becoming an increasingly prevalent issue. With the advent of various workplace distractions such as social media, computer games, and mobile phones, students have ample opportunities to postpone the completion of assignments, coursework, and theses. Many students are convinced that they will be able to accomplish everything if they start working on tasks tomorrow, but often this 'tomorrow' is indefinitely postponed. According to K. Lay, such procrastination of academic tasks is considered inadequate behavior, which can lead to psychological stress with a range of negative consequences, including increased anxiety, feelings of guilt, and decreased academic performance [1]. Examining the structural relationships

between academic procrastination and motivation in educational activities is an important step in understanding and addressing this issue.

In this research work, in addition to analyzing the issue of academic procrastination, the question of academic motivation is also illuminated. The choice of academic motivation as the object of study is justified by the fact that it is a key factor in optimizing the learning process. Studying the relationships between academic procrastination and academic motivation can contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of education [2]. It has long been noted that the interplay between motivational factors and procrastination significantly impacts the educational process in higher education institutions [3]. It is worth noting that several reports suggest that motivation influences procrastination, which, in turn, negatively affects students' success [4, 5].

Procrastination. Research on procrastination presents a plethora of definitions, akin to the number of researchers delving into this topic. However, recent studies [6] converge on the notion that procrastination is defined as the voluntary tendency to delay tasks, even at the expense of one's own well-being, which entails particularly adverse consequences for students, both academically and psychologically [7]. This underscores the importance of recognizing and managing procrastination as a significant aspect of students' academic and personal lives. Developing effective strategies to overcome procrastination can significantly enhance their academic performance and well-being, fostering the cultivation of better self-regulation and self-discipline skills. Additionally, many researchers argue that procrastination arises due to failure or lack of self-regulation [8, 9].

Academic Motivation. Self-Determination Theory distinguishes between two types of motivation - intrinsic and extrinsic, within the framework of self-regulation processes. This theory highlights various self-regulation methods, which can be represented along a continuum with varying degrees of self-control. Actions requiring a higher level of self-regulation are typically more adaptive than those

where the level of self-determination is lower. Based on this theory, it can be added that awareness of the differences between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation helps understand which factors influence our actions. Understanding various self-regulation methods and levels of self-control helps better organize one's life and achieve set goals. Additionally, understanding that actions requiring a higher level of self-regulation are typically more adaptive allows for improvement in productivity and success in various life domains.

In general, these types of motivation can be divided into three main categories.

A) Firstly, amotivation expresses a complete lack of motivation and a sense of loss of control over events, including feelings of incompetence and lack of purpose; it typically resides at the end of the motivational spectrum and indicates maladaptive lack of self-determination.

B) Secondly, extrinsic motivation lies in the middle of the spectrum, indicating that behavior is driven by external goals.

C) Finally, intrinsic motivation is situated at the self-determined end of the continuum, where the activity itself becomes the goal, and the driving force is the individual's internal desire [10].

Examples of these types of motivation:

1. Amotivation: A student sees no point in studying, lacks interest in the subject, and feels incapable of learning successfully. They have no clearly defined goals and fail to see the connection between their studies and their future.

2. Extrinsic motivation: A student studies a subject because they fear punishment from the teacher or parents if they don't complete assignments. Their driving force is an external stimulus rather than their own interest or satisfaction from learning.

3. Intrinsic motivation: A student is passionate about the subject and strives to understand its deeper aspects. They find satisfaction in the process of learning

and self-improvement, and their internal desire to learn and succeed is the primary driving force.

Additionally, Chang's study [11] revealed that both Intrinsic and Extrinsic motivation are significant predictors of procrastination: the former is associated with negative outcomes, while the latter is associated with positive outcomes. In light of this, researchers Bernam and colleagues [12] noted that motivation based on self-determination predicts negative manifestations of procrastination. Furthermore, Rebetz et al.'s research [13] indicates a strong and negative relationship between procrastination and identification with external motives, while other motivational variables do not have significant associations with procrastination. They suggest that only external regulation is capable of distinguishing procrastinators from other personality types. Additionally, Yurtseven and Dogan's study [14] found a direct link between procrastination and amotivation, but not with intrinsic or extrinsic motivation. Finally, there is evidence of a lack of significant correlation between procrastination and motivation in the educational context [15].

Academic Procrastination and Academic Motivation. Academic procrastination often arises as a result of insufficient or weak academic motivation. When students do not feel sufficient internal drive or interest in their studies, they tend to postpone tasks for later. Low academic motivation can be associated with various factors, such as inadequate understanding of learning goals, unsatisfactory results, fear of failure, or insufficient support from the environment. Conversely, active engagement and high levels of motivation can help students overcome procrastination, as they derive greater satisfaction from the learning process and consciously strive to achieve their goals. Regarding less self-determined motivational types, procrastination has been positively associated with internally motivated and internally regulated motivational types. Students who complete tasks out of internal resolution, aiming to achieve external goals, improve their

self-esteem, avoid anxiety and guilt, as well as overcome feelings of loss of control, may face an increased risk of procrastination. According to researchers, procrastination is associated with a motivation deficit and negative emotions such as guilt and anxiety [9, 16]. Furthermore, it should be noted that procrastination can be caused not only by a motivation deficit but also by other factors such as fear of failure, uncertainty about goals and tasks, perfectionism, and insufficient self-regulation. Research also suggests that procrastination can become a way of coping with unpleasant emotions and stress by postponing task completion [12, p. 732]. Therefore, for effective procrastination management, attention should be paid not only to the level of motivation but also to students' emotional state, stress management, and ways to overcome the anxieties associated with the learning process.

Conclusion. From the analysis of the aforementioned data, it is evident that procrastination represents a significant problem in the educational context, negatively impacting both students' academic performance and psychological well-being. This underscores the need for a deeper understanding and management of this phenomenon within the academic environment. Approaches to overcoming procrastination should include the development not only of motivational aspects but also the ability to manage emotional states and stress. It is also important to consider that factors such as fear of failure, uncertainty about goals and tasks, perfectionism, and insufficient self-regulation can play a significant role in the occurrence of procrastination. Thus, effective strategies for combating procrastination should take into account the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon and involve a comprehensive approach aimed at developing students' self-regulation skills, motivation management, and emotional regulation. Additionally, it should be noted that procrastination can be considered as a mechanism for coping with unpleasant emotions and stress by delaying task completion. In this context, attention should also be paid to students' emotional

state and the development of approaches to stress management, alleviating anxieties associated with the learning process, and enhancing their emotional resilience. It is also important to consider students' individual characteristics, needs, and preferences when developing methods to combat procrastination, which can contribute to increasing the effectiveness of approaches to managing this phenomenon in the academic environment.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Varvaricheva, Y.I. The Phenomenon of Procrastination: Problems and Research Perspectives. Y.I. Varvaricheva. Questions of Psychology. 2010. No. 3. pp. 121-131.
2. "Ilyin, E.O. Work and Personality: Workaholism, Perfectionism, Laziness. E.O. Ilyin. St. Petersburg: Piter, 2011. P. 224."
3. Senecal, C., Koestner, R., & Vallerand, R. J. (1995). Self-regulation and academic procrastination. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 135(5), 607–619. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.1995.9712234>
4. Klassen, R. M., Krawchuk, L. L., & Rajani, S. (2008). Academic procrastination of undergraduates: Low self-efficacy to self-regulate predicts higher levels of procrastination. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 33(4), 915–931. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2007.07.001>
5. Lindt, S. F., Corkin, D. M., & Yu, S. (2014). Using multiple methods to distinguish active delay and procrastination in college students. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 4(2), 28–32.
6. Steel, P. (2010). Arousal, avoidant and decisional procrastinators: Do they exist? *Personality and Individual Differences*, 48(8), 926–934. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2010.02.025>

7. Kim, K. R., & Seo, E. H. (2015). The relationship between procrastination and academic performance: A meta-analysis. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 82, 26–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2015.02.038>
8. Haghbin, M., McCaffrey, A., & Pychyl, T. A. (2012). The complexity of the relation between fear of failure and procrastination. *Journal of Rational-Emotive & Cognitive-Behavior Therapy*, 30(4), 249–263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10942-012-0153-9>
9. Klingsieck, K. B., Grund, A., Schmid, S., & Fries, S. (2013). Why students procrastinate: A qualitative approach. *Journal of College Student Development*, 54(4), 397–412. <https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.2013.0060>
10. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2013). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. Springer Science & Business Media.
11. Chang, H. K. (2014). Perfectionism, anxiety, and academic procrastination: The role of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in college students. Master's Thesis, San Bernardino. <https://scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/etd/28>
12. Mahdy, M. A. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the academic performance of veterinary medical students. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 7, 732. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.594261>
13. Rebetz, M. M. L., Rochat, L., & Van der Linden, M. (2015). Cognitive, emotional, and motivational factors related to procrastination: A cluster analytic approach. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 76, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2014.11.044>
14. Yurtseven, N., & Dogan, S. (2019). Structural relationships among academic procrastination, academic motivation, and problem solving skill in prep class college students. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, 9(3), 849–876. <https://doi.org/10.14527/pegegog.2019.027>

15. Yun, L. J. (2019). The Relationship between Academic Motivation and Academic Procrastination among University Students. Tunku Abdul Rahman University College.
16. Haghbin, M., McCaffrey, A., & Pychyl, T. A. (2012). The complexity of the relation between fear of failure and procrastination. *Journal of Rational-Emotive & Cognitive-Behavior Therapy*, 30(4), 249–263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10942-012-0153-9>